

Genetic analysis of the impact of heat stress on fertility traits in dairy cows in the Netherlands

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to use temperature-humidity index (THI) as an indicator for assessing heat stress conditions for fertility traits in the Holstein dairy cattle breed in the Netherlands. Data from AI and calving events of 416,814 first-parity cows from the Netherlands were used, considering different THI definitions based on different numbers of days before and after artificial insemination events. To achieve our aim, we investigated first, at population level, the relationship between different THI definitions and 4 fertility traits: conception rate, interval calving to first insemination, interval first to last insemination, and calving interval. Second, to investigate individual variation in the relationship between THI and fertility, variance components were estimated for each trait using the so-called broken stick model. This model assumes that breeding values are dependent on THI above but not below a THI threshold identified at the population level and explores the presence of genetic variation associated with fertility decline during heat stress. This study revealed considerable changes in fertility traits during periods of heat stress, with a THI threshold of 60 for conception rate and interval first to last insemination and 50 for interval calving to first insemination and calving interval. Interestingly, as THI levels increased, genetic variance and heritability also increased, indicating that at higher THI levels associated with reduced fertility, the genetic variation of fertility traits is greater. Furthermore, significant genotype-by-environment interactions were observed for all 4 fertility traits, suggesting changes in sire rankings between THI levels below and above the threshold. This study provides insights that may help breeding programs and farmers breed animals resilient to heat stress conditions.

Key words: temperature-humidity index, heat stress, fertility, genotype-by-environment interaction

INTRODUCTION

Across many countries, the livestock production industry faces a pressing issue of heat stress (HS; El-Tarabany et al., 2017), especially with the increased frequency and intensity of heatwaves (IPCC, 2021), and is likely attributed to global warming and climate change (Cheruiyot et al., 2020). Heat stress occurs when the surrounding temperature exceeds an animal's thermoneutral zone; under these conditions, animals must use extra energy to maintain their body temperature, which can impair performance (Becker et al., 2020). Also, high relative humidity leads to HS by impeding the evaporation of sweat, which is essential for heat dissipation (West, 2003). Dairy cows, for example, during periods of HS, may need to modify their physiological and behavioral processes to produce less heat and dissipate more heat during acclimatization (Yan et al., 2021), and although necessary for survival, this acclimatization reduces animal performance (e.g., milk production and fertility).

Different measures are used to evaluate the extent of HS experienced by dairy cows, which can be categorized as either animal-based measures, such as physiological and behavioral responses, or environmental measures, such as thermal indices (Herbut et al., 2018; Hoffmann et al., 2020). Among these, the temperature-humidity index (THI) is a popular environmental indicator for assessing HS conditions in dairy cattle (Ravagnolo and Misztal, 2000; Bohmanova et al., 2007). This index is a single value that combines both air temperature and relative humidity. Despite considering solely these 2 environmental factors, the THI frequently serves as a comprehensive indicator of the total effect of HS on animals (Hahn et al., 2009). Considering THI as defined by NRC (1971), several studies have shown that many cattle experience mild HS when the THI falls within the range of 60 to 72 or exceeds this range (Bohmanova et al., 2007; Brüge-

Received June 20, 2024.

Accepted October 7, 2024.

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The list of standard abbreviations for JDS is available at adsa.org/jds-abbreviations-24. Nonstandard abbreviations are available in the Notes.

mann et al., 2012; Ekine-Dzivenu et al., 2020; Mbutia et al., 2022), particularly in relation to production traits. If the THI levels surpass this range, the resulting HS can unfavorably affect performance in terms of, among others, milk production and fertility. Poor fertility is an important reason for culling; therefore, fertility is a crucial aspect of the economic success of dairy farming (González-Recio et al., 2004; De Vries, 2006; Sewalem et al., 2008).

The unfavorable effects of HS on the reproductive processes in dairy cows include the inhibition of the growth of ovarian follicles, synthesis of hormones (e.g., estrogen and progesterone), expression of estrus, oocyte competence, uterine endometrial response, and embryo development after fertilization, which have been well documented in various studies (Jordan, 2003; Hansen, 2009; Silva et al., 2013; Sigdel et al., 2020). Different HS mitigation strategies have been implemented to counteract these unfavorable effects, including shade provision, sprinklers, fans, sufficient water supply, and modifications in feeding and management (Sigdel et al., 2020). However, these methods may be costly and ineffective in pasture-based dairy systems where cows are exposed to direct sunlight while grazing. Recent studies show that the extensive selection of production traits in the last few decades has also unfavorably impacted the thermoregulatory ability of dairy cows (Aguilar et al., 2009; Santana et al., 2017; Sigdel et al., 2019). Taken together, these observations suggest that genetic selection for improved thermotolerance could be a viable complementary strategy for alleviating the unfavorable effects of HS aiming to boost reproductive performance (Pszczola et al., 2009) and, ultimately, longevity.

The effects of HS on various fertility traits are well documented (Carabaño et al., 2017; Roth, 2020), but it is also clear that there is a large variety in the THI thresholds, which marks the onset of HS across different geographical locations and production systems. Additionally, the genetic variation observed beyond the THI threshold may vary across populations as well. Therefore, to assess the impact of HS on fertility traits and the potential to mitigate this by genetic selection for a particular population or production system, a thorough genetic analysis is needed to estimate the required parameters.

This study aimed to investigate the impact of HS on 4 fertility traits, namely, conception rate (**CR**), interval calving to first insemination (**ICFI**), interval first to last insemination (**IFLI**), and calving interval (**CIV**) in the Holstein dairy cattle in the Netherlands. This was achieved as follows. First, at the population level, we identified the THI definition and the THI threshold that most appropriately marked the critical THI levels during which HS affects fertility. Second, at an individual level,

we used reaction norm models to investigate the genetic variation of fertility as a function of the experienced THI level.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Because no live animals were used in this study, Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee approval was not required. The data used in this study included pedigree, reproductive, and climatic data. The pedigree and reproductive data were provided by CRV (Arnhem, the Netherlands), encompassing cow records from Dutch dairy herds. The climatic data (i.e., temperature and relative humidity measurements) were extracted from the Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologisch Instituut (**KNMI**) website (<https://www.knmi.nl/>), spanning from 1990 onward.

Reproductive Data

The raw reproductive data included records from 739,169 Holstein heifers and cows that were inseminated between 2010 and 2022. The pedigree information spanned several generations, including 5,322,937 animals, with 103,259 sires and 2,209,036 dams. The raw data were edited such that (1) only first-parity cows with records were considered; (2) each fixed effect level (i.e., year-month, herd-year, day of the week of insemination, or sexed semen was associated with at least 5 records); (3) each THI level (defined as a unique rounded integer THI value) was associated with a minimum of 50 observations; and (4) only records of daughters of sires with a minimum of 5 daughters with records in the data were kept. After these edits, records of 416,814 first-parity cows remained. Pedigree of the sires of first-parity cows with records was then extracted, including 3 generations of ancestors.

The fertility traits used in this study were CR, ICFI, IFLI, and CIV. The CR was considered only for the first insemination and defined as follows: CR was assigned a value of 100 if there was no subsequent insemination, and when a gestation following the first insemination was between 45 and 300 d (considered as a pregnancy or a pregnancy followed by an abortion). The CR was assigned a value of 0 if there was a subsequent insemination, or if a gestation length of more than 300 d was recorded (which is considered as a pregnancy resulting from another insemination). The ICFI was calculated as the difference between the date of calving and the date of the first AI and thus measures a cow's ability to return to cyclic estrus after calving. The IFLI was defined as the number of days between the first and last AI, regardless of whether a next calving occurred. Records for ICFI

and the corresponding records for IFLI were included if ICFI had a value between 30 and 250 d. The CIV was calculated as the number of days between the first and second calving events. The CIV records retained for further analyses had to have a CIV value within the range of 250 to 800 d, and the corresponding first calving date had to be more than 18 mo before the last calving date in the dataset, to avoid bias due to incomplete data. The CIV values greater than 550 were set to 550, in line with the definition used in the national evaluations (CRV, 2023). Finally, to align the IFLI and CIV definitions, considering the maximum allowed value for CIV of 800 and an average gestation length of 280 d, IFLI records with values greater than 520 d were not included in the analyses.

Climatic Data

Weather-related information (i.e., temperature and relative humidity measurements) was collected from the nearest weather station to each dairy herd and was determined based on the partial postal codes of the herds. All 34 KNMI weather stations located on land within the Netherlands were considered. The average distance between the herds and the nearest weather station was 14.621 km, with a minimum distance of 0.221 km and a maximum distance of 36.089 km. The average daily THI was calculated using the formula proposed by NRC (1971):

$$(1.8 \times T + 32) - (0.55 - 0.0055 \times RH) \times (1.8 \times T - 26)$$

where T is the average daily temperature (°C), and RH is the average daily relative humidity (%).

Using those daily THI values, various definitions of THI values associated with the first AI events were developed (Table 1). These definitions included calculating the average THI values over specific days preceding and following AI events (Carabaño et al., 2017), as the THI value on the day of AI alone may not fully capture the impact of HS on the expression of fertility traits. The climatic data were then merged with the edited reproductive data based on date of the first AI in the first parity to test which of those THI definitions enabled to most clearly predict the critical period for each trait (i.e., the THI level associated with the beginning of a declined performance in these reproductive traits, following the approach described by Ravagnolo and Misztal [2000]). The final dataset consisted of 416,814 first-parity Holstein cows with AI records from 1,565 herds in the Netherlands, with a total of 4,988 sires with daughters in the dataset from 2010 to 2021. All the 416,814 first-parity Holstein cows had a record for CR, 416,793 had a

Table 1. Definitions of various heat stress indicators derived as averages of the temperature-humidity index (THI) over a specified number of days

Abbreviation	Total length (d)	Days before insemination	Days after insemination ¹
THI3	3	1	1
THI7	7	3	3
THI10	10	5	4
THI30	30	20	9
THI50	50	40	9

¹The number of days included after insemination is equal to total length – days before insemination – 1 (to account for the day of insemination).

retained record for ICFI, 416,726 had a retained record for IFLI, and 317,213 had a retained record for CIV. Because we used sire models, the final pedigree file included those 4,988 sires and their ancestors, comprising 15,123 pedigree records, with 2,420 unique sires and 11,505 unique dams.

The final datasets were analyzed using ASReml software version 4.2 (Gilmour et al., 2021), employing 2 sire models: the main effects model (**MEM**) to assess the overall phenotypic effect of HS on the fertility traits and identify the THI threshold that marks the onset of HS affecting fertility, and the broken stick model (**BSM**) to assess the existence of genetic variation in resilience to HS. For both models, the impact of using different THI definitions was evaluated.

Main Effects Model

The MEM can be written as follows:

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{X}\boldsymbol{\beta} + \mathbf{Z}\mathbf{a} + \mathbf{W}\mathbf{s} + \mathbf{e},$$

where \mathbf{y} represents the vector of phenotypes of one of the traits: CR, ICFI, IFLI, or CIV; $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ is the vector of fixed effects (described below); \mathbf{a} is the vector of random additive genetic effects of the sires; \mathbf{s} is the vector of random service sire effects (only included for CR); and \mathbf{e} is the vector of random residuals. \mathbf{X} is an incidence matrix connecting phenotypes to the corresponding fixed effects; \mathbf{W} is an incidence matrix connecting the phenotypes to the corresponding service sire effects (3,720 levels); and \mathbf{Z} is an incidence matrix connecting the phenotypes to the corresponding additive genetic sire effects (4,988 levels). The fixed effects included varied across traits, following the models used in the Dutch/Flemish genetic evaluations (CRV, 2023). For CR, this included herd-year (16,092 levels), year-month (134 levels), and weekday (7 levels) of AI, and sexed semen (3 levels: conventional, sexed semen, unknown). For IFLI the model included herd-year (16,092 levels) and year-month (134 levels)

of AI. For ICFI and CIV, the model included herd-year (17,668 levels for ICFI and 17,080 levels for CIV) and year-month (141 levels for ICFI and 132 levels for CIV) of calving. Finally, for all 4 traits, a fixed class effect for THI surrounding first insemination as defined in Table 1 was included, where each rounded integer THI value was considered as a separate level.

The MEM was applied for each combination of the 5 THI definitions surrounding the first insemination and the 4 fertility traits. For each THI definition, the estimated effect of each THI level was then plotted against the THI level to identify the THI threshold that marks the onset of HS. The selection of the most appropriate THI definitions was based on the P -values associated with the fixed effect for the different THI level definitions ($P < 0.05$) and the clarity of the patterns observed in the visual representation of the relationships between the estimated effect of each THI level and the THI level for every significant THI definition.

Broken Stick Model

The BSM was implemented using, for each of the 4 traits, the most suitable THI definition and the corresponding threshold that was identified using the MEM. Following previous studies (e.g., Bohmanova et al., 2007; Ravagnolo and Misztal, 2000), the BSM is written as follows:

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{X}\boldsymbol{\beta} + \mathbf{Z}_0\mathbf{a}_0 + \mathbf{Z}_1\mathbf{a}_1 + \mathbf{W}\mathbf{s} + \mathbf{e},$$

where $\mathbf{X}\boldsymbol{\beta}$, $\mathbf{W}\mathbf{s}$, and \mathbf{e} were similarly defined as in the MEM model; \mathbf{a}_0 is the vector of random additive genetic sire effects for the intercept; \mathbf{a}_1 is the vector of random additive genetic sire effects for the slope; \mathbf{Z}_0 is an incidence matrix connecting the phenotypes to the corresponding \mathbf{a}_0 (intercept); and \mathbf{Z}_1 is a matrix of covariates with each row containing one value to reflect the THI (as explained hereafter) associated with the record to connect the phenotypes with \mathbf{a}_1 and zeros otherwise. The BSM considered the same fixed effects as the MEM, except for THI, which in this case was modeled as a fixed regression rather than as a fixed class effect. The THI covariates for the fixed regression were determined for each trait from the results of the MEM, and are described in the Results section.

Note that the sire effect estimated with the sire model, also known as PTA, should be multiplied by 2 to obtain the sire EBV. Thus, the EBV of sire i was modeled as a linear function of THI, using $\text{EBV}_{i,\text{THI}_j} = 2z_{0,\text{THI}}\hat{a}_{0,i} + 2z_{1,\text{THI}_j}\hat{a}_{1,i}$, where $\hat{a}_{0,i}$ and $\hat{a}_{1,i}$ are, respectively, the estimated sire effects for the intercept and slope of sire i ; $z_{0,\text{THI}}$ has a value of one for all THI

values; and z_{1,THI_j} is a normalized covariate for THI value

THI_j . It was assumed that there was no HS effect on the trait at THI values below the THI threshold. The normalized covariate for THI value THI_j was computed as

$$z_{1,\text{THI}_j} = \frac{\max\left[(\text{THI}_j - \text{threshold}), 0\right]}{\max(\text{THI}) - \text{threshold}}.$$

Modeling the EBV as random regressions on THI implies that the genetic variances are heterogeneous across THI levels. To also allow the residual variances to be heterogeneous, they were estimated separately for 4 classes with different ranges of THI values. To define those classes, the THI levels were sorted and grouped for each trait based on the identified thresholds from the MEM. For the traits CR, and IFLI, the classes were defined as follows: $\text{THI} < 60$, $60 \leq \text{THI} < 65$, $65 \leq \text{THI} < 70$, and $\text{THI} \geq 70$. For the traits ICFI and CIV, however, the classes were divided based on a THI threshold of 50: $\text{THI} < 50$, $50 \leq \text{THI} < 60$, $60 \leq \text{THI} < 70$, and $\text{THI} \geq 70$.

To determine whether modeling the EBV for slope provided a significantly better fit to the data, the BSM was also applied while excluding the additive genetic effect of the slope (\mathbf{a}_1), to create a reduced model. The log-likelihoods of both models (with and without the EBV for slope) were compared using the log-likelihood ratio test (Gilmour et al., 2021). The log-likelihood ratio test assesses the difference in fit between the full model (including the EBV for slope) and the reduced model. The test statistic D was calculated as:

$$D = 2\log(l_{R2}/l_{R1}) = 2[\log(l_{R2}) - \log(l_{R1})],$$

where $\log(l_{R2})$ is the log-likelihood value of the full model, and $\log(l_{R1})$ is the log-likelihood value of the reduced model. The resulting log-likelihood ratio (D) follows a mixture of 2 Chi-squared (χ^2) distributions with 1 and 2 df (Visscher, 2006). Based on this, the P -value for an observed value d for the D statistic was approximated as: $\left\{1 - 0.5\left[\text{Prob}\left(X_2^2 \leq d\right) + \text{Prob}\left(X_1^2 \leq d\right)\right]\right\}$.

The estimated sire variance at THI value THI_j was computed using the following formula:

$$\hat{\sigma}_{s,\text{THI}_j}^2 = \hat{\sigma}_{s,0}^2 + 2 \times z_{1,\text{THI}_j} \hat{\sigma}_{s,0;s,1} + \left(z_{1,\text{THI}_j}\right)^2 \times \hat{\sigma}_{s,1}^2,$$

where $\hat{\sigma}_{s,\text{THI}_j}^2$ is the estimated sire variance at THI value THI_j , $\hat{\sigma}_{s,0}^2$ is the estimated sire variance of the intercept, $\hat{\sigma}_{s,0;s,1}$ is the estimated covariance between the sire breeding values for intercept and slope, z_{1,THI_j} is the normalized THI value corresponding to THI_j , and $\hat{\sigma}_{s,1}^2$ is the estimated sire variance of the slope.

The estimated heritability at THI value THI_j was computed as:

$$\hat{h}_{\text{THI}_j}^2 = \frac{4\hat{\sigma}_{s,\text{THI}_j}^2}{\hat{\sigma}_{s,\text{THI}_j}^2 + \hat{\sigma}_{e,\text{THI}_j}^2},$$

where $\hat{\sigma}_{e,\text{THI}_j}^2$ represents the residual variance estimated for the class to which THI_j was assigned. Finally, within each THI definition and trait, the estimated genetic correlations between THI levels THI_j and THI_k were calculated using the following formula:

$$\hat{r}_{g,\text{THI}_j;\text{THI}_k} = \frac{\hat{\sigma}_{s,\text{THI}_j;s,\text{THI}_k}}{\hat{\sigma}_{s,\text{THI}_j} \hat{\sigma}_{s,\text{THI}_k}},$$

where the estimated covariance $\hat{\sigma}_{s,\text{THI}_j;s,\text{THI}_k}$ was computed as follows:

$$\hat{\sigma}_{s,\text{THI}_j;s,\text{THI}_k} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & z_{1,\text{THI}_j} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\sigma}_{s,0}^2 & \hat{\sigma}_{s,0;s,1} \\ \hat{\sigma}_{s,0;s,1} & \hat{\sigma}_{s,1}^2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ z_{1,\text{THI}_k} \end{bmatrix}.$$

Standard errors of the genetic correlations were approximated as described by Fischer et al. (2004), using the implementation in ASReml (Gilmour et al., 2021).

RESULTS

Data Summary Statistics

Details of the summary statistics of the data collected for the fertility traits in the Dutch Holstein population are presented in Table 2. The average CR indicates the percentage of successful conceptions after first insemination, which was 45.80%. ICFI represents the time duration between calving and the first insemination, averaging 81.35 d; IFLI, which reflects the period between the first and last insemination attempts had an average of 37.78 d. Lastly, CIV denotes the number of days between the first and second calving events, averaging 391.30 d.

Table 2. Data summary of fertility traits in the Dutch Holstein cattle population

Trait	Average performance	SD	Minimum	Maximum
CR (%)	45.80	49.82	0	100
ICFI (d)	81.35	31.89	30	250
IFLI (d)	37.78	58.32	0	519
CIV (d)	391.30	55.40	250	550

CR = conception rate; ICFI = interval calving to first insemination; IFLI = interval first to last insemination; CIV = calving interval.

Figure 1. Distribution of THI3 values associated with the 416,814 records for CR.

The distribution of observed THI values across 3 days surrounding first insemination (**THI3**) values associated with the CR records is shown in Figure 1. In total, 49.0%, 22.9%, and 1.1% of the records were associated with THI values equal to or greater than 50, 60, and 70, respectively.

Effect of THI on Fertility Traits at a Population Level

The effect of THI on the fertility traits at the population level was investigated using the MEM analysis. The *P*-values for the estimated THI effects showed that THI averaged across 3 (**THI3**), 7 (**THI7**), or 10 (**THI10**) in almost all cases significantly affected all 4 traits (Table 3). In addition, THI averaged across 30 and 50 days surrounding first insemination significantly affected performance of 3 out of the 4 traits. Figure 2 depicts the relationship between the average performance of each of the fertility traits and levels of THI3, THI7, and THI10. Considering those 3 THI definitions, for values within the thermoneutral range of 30 to 60, both CR and IFLI showed optimal performance. Beyond THI 60, both CR and IFLI deteriorated. The CR decreased as much as ~10% between THI of 60 and 70, and IFLI increased up to 5 d between THI of 60 and 70. Both traits further deteriorated after a THI of 70. Compared with the other traits, ICFI showed a close to linear relationship with THI, showing an increase of about 6 d in the THI range from 35 to 65. The CIV demonstrated a stable performance within the THI range of 35 to 50. Between THI 50 and 70, there was an increase in CIV of about 12 d. It should be noted that the irregular patterns at the extremities observed for all 4 traits in Figure 2 likely are due to a smaller sample size of animals exposed to these extreme THI levels. The THI thresholds after which the average performance became

Table 3. *P*-values for each of the THI definitions (as defined in Table 1) obtained using the main effects model for each of the 4 traits¹

Definition	<i>P</i> -value			
	CR	ICFI	IFLI	CIV
THI3	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
THI7	<0.001	<0.001	0.058	<0.001
THI10	<0.001	<0.001	0.002	<0.001
THI30	<0.001	<0.001	0.261	<0.001
THI50	0.005	<0.001	0.086	<0.001

¹THI = temperature-humidity index; CR = conception rate; ICFI = interval calving to first insemination; IFLI = interval first to last insemination; CIV = calving interval.

poorer were identified to be 60 for CR and IFLI, and 50 for CIV, whereas no threshold was identified for ICFI. Based on these thresholds, a fixed regression curve was parameterized in the BSM to model the overall pattern across levels. To capture the curvilinear relationship observed between THI values above the threshold and the change in the traits CR and IFLI, for those 2 traits the THI covariates for the BSM above the THI threshold of 60 were computed as the square of the normalized THI values. For CIV the covariates above the threshold of 50 were equal to the normalized THI values, to capture the observed linear relationship. For CR, IFLI, and CIV, the covariates below the thresholds were equal to 0. Finally, for ICFI the covariates were a linear transformation of all THI values, without considering a THI threshold, to reflect the observed close to linear relationship across the entire THI range. The patterns of these curves estimated with the BSM for THI3 generally agreed well with the patterns estimated with the MEM (Figure 2).

Effect of THI on Fertility Traits at an Individual Level

The BSM was implemented for THI3, THI7, and THI10, as the MEM analysis showed that these THI definitions had a significant ($P < 0.05$) effect in nearly all combinations with the 4 traits. Given the low number of observations at extreme THI values, and the irregular estimates of the MEM at those extreme values, all THI values below 30 were set to 30, and THI values above 70 were set to 70, before being used in the fixed and random regressions in the BSM. For the random sire effects, the BSM used a THI threshold of 60 for CR and IFLI, and 50 for CIV, as identified by the MEM model. Initially, for ICFI a model with a linear random regression on THI was implemented, which is equivalent to a BSM without a THI threshold. This model, however, resulted in unexpected patterns of the estimated genetic variance, suggesting that the genetic variance is minimal at THI of ~45 (Supplemental Figure S1, see Notes). To mitigate these unexpected results, we decided to implement the BSM using the lowest THI threshold of 50, identified across

the other 3 traits. The log-likelihood ratio test comparing the full BSM to its reduced counterpart, showed that nearly all *P*-values were below 0.05 (Table 4), indicating that the full BSM generally provided a better fit to the data than the reduced model.

Estimation of Genetic Parameters

Variance components for all 4 traits for THI3, THI7, and THI10, estimated with the BSM, are presented in Table 5. The service sire effect explained less than 0.5% of the phenotypic variance of CR. For increasing THI values, the residual variances generally decreased for CR and IFLI, but generally increased for ICFI and CIV. Corresponding values for the reduced model were generally similar, but the reduced model showed a slightly higher sire variance compared with the sire intercept variance obtained with the BSM (results not shown). Genetic variances computed from the BSM results for each fertility trait clearly increased beyond the identified THI thresholds for all THI definitions (Figure 3). Patterns of genetic variances were very similar across THI definitions. Estimated heritabilities for the BSM are presented in Figure 4. At the thermoneutral level (i.e., at THI levels between an assumed value of 30 and the thresholds of 50 or 60) the heritability estimates were lowest for CR at ~0.02, and highest for ICFI at ~0.09. Similar to the genetic variances, the heritability estimates increased considerably for all 4 traits after the THI thresholds, with the highest increase observed for ICFI, in agreement with the large observed sire slope variance (Table 5). Genetic correlations between intercept and slope all had small positive values, but were all not significantly different from zero, given that the SE were close to or greater than the estimates themselves (Table 6).

Genotype-by-Environment Interactions

The genetic correlations between the different levels of THI3 are presented in Figure 5 for each of the traits. The genetic correlations indicate the level of the genotype-by-environment interactions. The majority of the estimated genetic correlations were higher than 0.80. However, the lowest correlations of 0.49 and 0.79 were observed between THI 50 or 60 and THI 70 for the traits ICFI and CR respectively. For IFLI, the correlations ranged from 0.84 to 1.00, and for CIV they ranged from 0.86 to 1.00. Standard errors of the estimated genetic correlations were relatively low (Table 7), suggesting that any of those genetic correlations below ~0.9 were significantly different from unity.

Figure 6 shows the effect of increasing THI3 levels on the sire EBV for 30 sires in each trait, showing reranking between those sires across THI levels. These sires

Figure 2. Effects of THI3, THI7, and THI10 (as defined in Table 1) on conception rate, interval calving to first insemination, interval first to last insemination, and calving interval.

were selected based on having the highest reliability for the EBV of the slope. Under thermoneutral conditions (i.e., for THI between 30 and 50 or 60), the ranking of sires remained the same, as a result of the BSM model parametrization. From THI 50 or 60 onwards, reranking

occurred for all 4 traits. These patterns were in agreement with the observed genetic correlations between different THI levels (Figure 5).

DISCUSSION

Effect of THI on Fertility Traits

The objectives of our study were to estimate the effect of THI on fertility traits (CR, ICFI, IFLI, and CIV) in first-parity Holstein cattle in the Netherlands, to identify the best definition of THI to model this effect, and to determine the THI levels at which HS begins to affect these traits. Using the average THI values of the day of insemination and 1 d before and after the insemination (THI3) enabled us to most clearly model the impact of THI on fertility. Our results from the fixed regression in the BSM indicate that at the population level with in-

Table 4. P-values of the log-likelihood ratio test comparing the broken stick model to the reduced model¹

Trait	THI definition		
	THI3	THI7	THI10
CR	0.0082	0.0304	0.0858
ICFI	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001
IFLI	<0.0001	0.0002	0.0208
CIV	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001

¹THI = temperature-humidity index; CR = conception rate; ICFI = interval calving to first insemination; IFLI = interval first to last insemination; CIV = calving interval.

Table 5. Estimated variances and covariances for the broken stick model¹

Variance	CR				ICFI			IFLI			CIV		
	THI3	THI7	THI10	THI3	THI7	THI10	THI3	THI7	THI10	THI3	THI7	THI10	
Service sire	7.89	7.88	7.87	711.11	707.40	708.45	3,300.08	3,294.86	3,295.93	2,743.32	2,734.71	2,737.29	
Residual 1 ²	2,404.87	2,404.71	2,404.82	839.82	844.31	837.80	3,236.69	3,268.49	3,264.84	2,855.65	2,859.53	2,847.43	
Residual 2	2,410.84	2,412.20	2,411.70	921.42	922.05	927.59	3,259.78	3,225.45	3,223.84	2,904.29	2,919.74	2,929.64	
Residual 3	2,383.51	2,365.11	2,360.29	811.89	777.04	717.24	3,047.50	3,022.06	2,906.60	2,934.74	2,896.43	2,870.95	
Residual 4	2,211.49	2,189.94	2,172.45	15.26	15.34	15.74	34.58	34.91	34.86	43.60	43.86	43.94	
Sire (intercept)	13.83	14.00	13.95	2.10	0.91	-0.76	1.90	-0.16	-0.01	5.03	4.25	3.93	
Sire covariance	0.93	-0.13	0.27	0.07	0.03	-0.02	0.08	-0.01	0.00	0.17	0.14	0.12	
Sire correlation	0.08	-0.01	0.03	61.80	76.37	84.05	16.40	16.57	14.92	19.74	21.31	22.83	
Sire (slope)	9.42	8.72	7.76										

¹THI = temperature-humidity index; CR = conception rate; ICFI = interval calving to first insemination; IFLI = interval first to last insemination; CIV = calving interval.

²For CR and IFLI, the residual variance classes were defined as follows: THI <60, 60 ≤ THI <65, 65 ≤ THI <70, and THI ≥70. For ICFI and CIV, this was: THI <50, 50 ≤ THI <60, 60 ≤ THI <70, and THI ≥70. The number of records included in each class, are described in Supplemental Table S1 (see Notes).

creasing THI levels, an unfavorable effect on the evaluated fertility traits occurs, for CR and IFLI at THI values greater than 60, for CIV at THI values greater than 50, albeit there were some changes below 50, and for ICFI values throughout the THI range from 30 to 70 (Figure 2). Our results from the random regression in the BSM indicated genetic variance of all 4 traits is considerably increased at THI values above the identified thresholds. For ICFI we initially did not model a THI threshold for the random genetic sire effect, and observed that the linear random regression model yielded increasing estimated genetic variances at both low and high THI levels (Supplemental Figure S1), which likely is an artifact of the linear random regression model. After implementing a THI threshold of 50, the pattern of the genetic variance at THI values above 50 agreed well with those of the linear regression model, whereas the genetic variance below 50 was constant as constrained by the BSM. As these results seemed more sensible, we used the BSM for ICFI for the main results presented in our study.

One reason for the decline in fertility during hot periods could be attributed to the influence of environmental heat and the associated physiological stress, which together alter the production of reproductive hormones (Hahn et al., 2003). HS during the summer months can further disrupt the follicular environment in highly productive dairy cows, leading to detrimental effects on pregnancy establishment and maintenance after fertilization (Wolfenson et al., 2000). Several studies (Roth, 2020; Miętkiewska et al., 2022; Kawano et al., 2022) suggest that oocytes are particularly sensitive to HS during the early stages of folliculogenesis, making them susceptible to damage. In fact, it has been found that oocytes can be affected by HS even in their earliest developmental stages. This suggests that in addition to the THI around first insemination, the THI at earlier moments, such as at the previous calving, may affect how long it takes for a cow to start cycling again, and thus possibly also ICFI and CIV. To test this, we fitted the MEM to THI3, THI7, and THI10 values that were calculated using the same definition as in Table 1, but now surrounding calving date instead of date of first insemination. The results show that using THI at the previous calving, there actually is no noticeable THI threshold after which ICFI and CIV are affected (Supplemental Figure S2, see Notes), suggesting that these traits are more affected by the THI at first insemination than at the previous calving.

Additionally, the embryo is highly vulnerable to HS within the first 7 d of its development and is more likely to fail to be maintained by the cow (Hansen, 2019). This susceptibility to HS can have a direct effect on the CR, potentially prolonging the CIV, as cows may require re-insemination to achieve successful conception. This high sensitivity of embryos to HS in the first few days of

Figure 3. Estimated genetic variances for conception rate, interval calving to first insemination, interval first to last insemination, and calving interval as a function of THI3, THI7, and THI10 (as defined in Table 1).

development, aligns with our observation that THI3 was one of the best THI definitions to model the effect of HS on fertility.

Other studies have shown that HS has an unfavorable effect on the CR of lactating dairy cows, with different thresholds identified for this trait. Schüller et al. (2014) identified a THI threshold of 73 in Germany, Ravagnolo and Misztal (2002a) identified a threshold of 70 in the United States, and Morton et al. (2007) identified a threshold of 72 in Australia. Similarly, Cartmill et al. (2001) found that when THI exceeded 72 in the United States, fewer cows showed estrus, leading to a lower CR. Garcia-Ispierto et al. (2007) found that the CR of Holstein cows in Northeastern Spain declined considerably when the THI reached 80 between 1 and 3 d before AI, resulting in a decline of CR by 7.6%. Djelailia et al. (2020) identified a THI threshold of 70 for CR, ICFI, and

CIV in Tunisia. HS during AI has been associated with significantly extended CIV in Egypt (El-Tarabany and El-Tarabany, 2015). Similarly, Halli et al. (2020) found that CIV in Germany was longest when the THI exceeded 60. These findings highlight the variability in THI thresholds for CR, ICFI, and CIV under HS conditions across different regions and studies. There are various factors that might contribute to the relatively low THI threshold observed across the traits in our study compared with other studies. Many of the studies with high thresholds for these traits concern animals that are raised in intensive farming systems (Vinet et al., 2023), which might have less grazing than dairy herds in the Netherlands, and at the same time more often have cooling systems in place that reduce the impact of high outdoor temperatures (Carabaño et al., 2014; Bernabucci et al., 2015). In the Netherlands fewer days of high THI occur compared

Figure 4. Heritability estimates for conception rate, interval first to last insemination, interval calving to first insemination, and calving interval as a function of THI3, THI7, and THI10 (as defined in Table 1).

with some of the other countries, which implies that likely fewer management measures to mitigate HS are taken. In our study, only 1.1% of the records were associated with THI values greater than 70, whereas the maximum THI value recorded over a specific number of days was 75. However, in countries such as Italy (Bernabucci et al., 2014), Spain, and the United States (Sánchez et al.,

2009), THI values can exceed this value and therefore the animals raised in production systems in those countries have more opportunities to acclimatize to high THI values and acquire a higher degree of thermotolerance, or could even have been bred for heat tolerance indirectly (Vinet et al., 2023). This may be an explanation why animals raised in these regions can more successfully reproduce under warmer conditions.

Table 6. Estimated genetic correlations (r_g) for THI3 between intercept and slope¹

Trait	r_g	SE
CR	0.081	0.189
ICFI	0.069	0.071
IFLI	0.080	0.173
CIV	0.171	0.144

¹THI = temperature-humidity index; CR = conception rate; ICFI = interval calving to first insemination; IFLI = interval first to last insemination; CIV = calving interval.

Estimated Variances and Heritabilities

Estimated heritabilities in our study in the thermoneutral zone were generally within the ranges reported in the literature, and very close to the estimates used in the Dutch/Flemish genetic evaluations (CRV, 2023). Our estimated heritability in the thermoneutral zone for CR of 0.02 was in the reported range of 0.01 to 0.17 (Pryce and Veerkamp 2001; Berry et al., 2014; Hagiya et al., 2017;

Figure 5. Estimates of genetic correlations between different THI3 (as defined in Table 1) levels for conception rate, interval calving to first insemination, interval first to last insemination, and calving interval.

Liu et al., 2017; Muuttoraanta et al., 2019); our estimated heritability for ICFI of 0.09 also falls within the reported range of 0.02 to 0.11 (Pryce and Veerkamp 2001; Berry et al., 2014; Liu et al., 2017; Muuttoraanta et al., 2019); our estimated heritability for CIV of 0.07 was in the reported range of 0.01 to 0.07 (Pryce et al., 2001; Veerkamp et al.,

2001; Wall et al., 2003; Mostert et al., 2010; Berry et al., 2014; Rahbar et al., 2016); and our estimated heritability in the thermoneutral zone for IFLI of 0.04 was in the reported range of 0.01 to 0.07 (Pryce and Veerkamp 2001; Sun et al., 2009; De Haer et al., 2010; Berry et al., 2014).

Our estimated heritabilities all increased with increasing THI levels beyond the threshold of 50 or 60, mostly as a result of increases in genetic variances. Relatively few heritabilities are reported in the literature for fertility traits under HS conditions. Sigdel et al. (2020) found heritability estimates between 0.024 and 0.032 for CR in Holstein cattle at THI of 78 in the state of Florida. Results from Ravagnolo and Misztal (2002b), also based on first-parity Holsteins in Florida, suggested beyond THI 70 a small increase in estimated heritability for non-return rate 90 d after insemination, but a considerable decrease in estimated heritability for nonreturn rate 90 d after insemination, decreasing from 0.053 at THI 70 to

Table 7. Estimated genetic correlations (r_g) between environments with THI3 values of 50 versus 65 or 70¹

Trait	THI 50 and 65		THI 50 and 70	
	r_g	SE	r_g	SE
CR	0.957	0.021	0.861	0.061
ICFI	0.644	0.043	0.544	0.052
IFLI	0.969	0.013	0.895	0.040
CIV	0.929	0.023	0.888	0.036

¹CR = conception rate; ICFI = interval calving to first insemination; IFLI = interval first to last insemination; CIV = calving interval.

Figure 6. Estimated breeding values (EBV) of the 30 sires with the most accurate slope EBV, estimated with the broken stick model for conception rate, interval calving to first insemination, interval first to last insemination, and calving interval, as a function of THI3 (as defined in Table 1).

below 0.01 at THI 80. Results from Biffani et al. (2016), based on Holstein cows in Italy, showed a small increase in estimated heritability for nonreturn rate at 56 d after first insemination for THI values greater than 73. Vinet et al. (2024) estimated heritabilities for CR in France that increased from 0.025 at THI 50 to 0.033 at THI 70 in Holstein, and from 0.014 at THI 50 to 0.020 at THI 70 in Montbeliarde. Although results are not fully consistent across studies, there seems to be a tendency of increased heritability for fertility traits under HS conditions, suggesting that genetic selection for improved fertility under HS conditions has potential.

Genotype-by-Environment Interactions

Resilient animals, characterized by their minimal susceptibility to environmental disturbances, exhibit con-

sistent performances under varying environmental conditions (Colditz and Hine, 2016; Berghof et al., 2019). Variation in the susceptibility to environmental changes become visible at the population level in terms of genotype-by-environment interactions. In models as applied in our study, these can be observed from the genetic correlation between the intercept and the slope of the breeding values, as well as the genetic correlation between the same trait expressed at different THI levels. For all traits, we observed a low positive genetic correlation between the intercept and slope, suggesting that there is only a limited relationship between the fertility of animals in the thermoneutral zone, and the degree to which their fertility is affected under HS conditions. This is in line with the estimated genetic correlations between intercept and slope for CR of -0.03 for Holstein in France (Vinet et al., 2024). Other studies actually reported generally

moderately negative genetic correlations between intercept and slope (Ravagnolo and Misztal, 2002b; Biffani et al., 2016), suggesting that the fertility of animals with the best performance in the thermoneutral zone, actually declines relatively more than the fertility of animals with poorer performance.

In our study, genetic correlations within the traits CR, IFLI, and CIV ranged from 0.86 to 0.90 between THI values below the threshold of 50 and 60 versus a THI of 70 (Table 7), and higher between THI values closer together (Figure 5). For ICFI, genetic correlations were as low as 0.64 and 0.51 between a THI value of 50 and THI values of 65 and 70, respectively. This may suggest that ICFI is the most suitable trait that captures the effect of HS on fertility. It is, however, not clear if this deviating result for ICFI is possibly due to an artifact of the modeling, given the overall linear relationship with THI that was not observed for the other traits (Figure 2). Our generally high genetic correlations are in line with those observed for Holsteins in France by Vinet et al. (2024). Nevertheless, the observed genetic correlations suggest there is some meaningful reranking of animals between the thermoneutral zone and the more severe HS conditions, which is indeed observed when examining the sire EBVs before and after the THI threshold established for each trait (Figure 6). The observed genotype-by-environment interaction, combined with the potential decline in genetic merit for heat tolerance in dairy cattle breeding (Nguyen et al., 2016), emphasizes the importance of considering resilience to HS in breeding programs.

In our study, we limited the analysis to first-parity cows, to avoid complexity due to heterogeneity of variances across parities, as well as fertility traits in different parities not having a unity genetic correlation between them (Jansen et al., 1987; Muuttoranta et al., 2019). The effect of HS on multiparous cows could be expected to be larger, given the increasing milk production at higher parity, which may increase the trade-off between milk production and fertility. At least for milk production traits, there seems to be a tendency that the genetic correlation between intercept and slope becomes more negative at higher parities (Carabaño et al., 2017).

To address the varying performances of sires under different environmental conditions, it is recommended to implement a genetic evaluation and ranking system that incorporates relevant environmental variables. Such a system can guide breeders in selecting sires that are better suited for regions with climatic conditions that frequently exceed thermal comfort thresholds (Kolmodin et al., 2002; Bryant et al., 2007; Nguyen et al., 2016). Additionally, incorporating HS tolerance into breeding strategies can enhance the flexibility and adaptability of cattle, ultimately improving the resilience and performance of future generations (Cheruiyot et al., 2020).

CONCLUSIONS

This study reveals a clear effect of HS on fertility traits of first-parity Holstein cows in the Netherlands, specifically a decrease in CR and an increase in interval traits. These effects were more pronounced when the THI threshold marking the onset of HS was computed as the average of THI values across a shorter period of time surrounding the day of insemination. The identified THI threshold was 60 for CR and IFLI, and 50 for ICFI and CIV. Our results highlight the presence of genetic variation in response to HS, with genetic effects becoming more pronounced at higher THI levels for all traits studied, which suggests the potential to use this variation to breed heat-resilient animals to improve fertility traits.

NOTES

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme for Research & Innovation under grant agreement no. 101000226 (Rumigen, Europe). Rumigen is part of EuroFAANG (<https://eurofaang.eu>). The funder had no role in the design, data collection, data analysis, and reporting of this study. Supplemental material for this article is available at <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.27798219>. No human or animal subjects were used, so this analysis did not require approval by an Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee or Institutional Review Board. Mathijs van Pelt is employed by Cooperation CRV. The other authors have not stated any conflicts of interest.

Nonstandard abbreviations used: BSM = broken stick model; CIV = calving interval; CR = conception rate; HS = heat stress; ICFI = interval calving to first insemination; IFLI = interval first to last insemination; KNMI = Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologisch Instituut; MEM = main effects model; r_g = estimated genetic correlation; THI = temperature-humidity index; THI3 = THI values across 3 d surrounding first insemination; THI7 = THI values across 3 d surrounding first insemination; THI10 = THI values across 3 d surrounding first insemination.

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